

ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FLUIDITY AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT IN HOMOLOGOUS SERIES. A NOTE

BY ASOKE KUMAR MUKHERJEE

It has been shown from theoretical considerations that fluidities of substances in a certain homologous series should be compared for the same value of ηT . At this condition fluidity is a function of molecular weight. The nature of the function has been determined by an appeal to experiments whence it is found that under the above condition it is a linear function.

Thomas Graham (*Ann. Chem. Pharm.*, 1863, 123, 90) suggested that there should be some regularity in the change of viscosity in passing from a lower to a higher member of any homologous series analogous to the rise in boiling point observed by Kopp. The observations of Thorpe and Rodgers (vide Hatschek, "The Viscosity of Liquids", 1928) in a way corroborate these suggestions. They compared viscosities of liquids of the same homologous series at their boiling points and also at temperatures at which the temperature coefficient of viscosity ($d\eta/dt$) had the same value by the help of $\eta-t$ curves and attempted a quantitative correlation by introducing a term "molecular viscosity" $\eta \cdot V^{2/3}$ where V represents the molecular volume of the liquid. A comparison of molecular viscosities at equal ($d\eta/dt$) revealed a regular increase of this quantity with a regular increase of CH_2 groups. The first member of the homologous series, of course, showed slight anomalies but the increment of molecular viscosity centred round a mean value of 120×10^{-4} units. Bingham (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 66, 1) from fluidity-temperature curves compared the temperatures of equal fluidity for a member of the same homologous series and observed them increasing regularly with each addition of CH_2 group in the case of non-associated liquids.

All these attempts, however, led to empirical results. McLeod (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 151) was of opinion that if the idea that viscosity of a liquid was inversely proportional to the free space was strictly correct, the problem would be best attacked by comparing viscosities at temperatures of equal free space. From a study of several homologous series he came to the conclusion that viscosity of a liquid was a linear function of molecular weight and inversely proportional to the free space. This marks the first attempt at a rational quantitative attack on this problem.

Since then various attempts have been made with a view to unravelling the true nature of the relationship between viscosity and molecular weight in the homologous series. Of these, the concept of rheochor, as proposed by Friend (*Nature*, 1942, 160, 432), deserves special mention. Other attempts all led to empirical relations and as such they contribute very little to the elucidation of the general mechanism of viscous flow. In the present paper an attempt has been made to attack this problem from a theoretical point of view and an equation has been presented connecting fluidity and molecular weight.

It has been shown in two previous communications (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 599; 1949, 26, 493) that the fluidity (ϕ) of a substance may be connected with temperature through the coefficient of thermal expansion (α). The equation is of the form

$$a + b\phi = \exp(\alpha T) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a and b are constants and are given by,

$$a = \exp(\alpha T_s) \text{ and } b = a/C.V_s$$

where V_s , T_s , and C are constants for the liquid. It has also been shown that a is a constant for a particular homologous series. Comparing two liquids of the same series at equal $\exp(\alpha T)$ we get,

$$a + b_1\phi_1 = \exp(\alpha_1 T_1) = \exp(\alpha_2 T_2) = a + b_2\phi_2$$

whence it follows, that at equal $\exp(\alpha T)$

$$b_1\phi_1 = b_2\phi_2.$$

i.e., for a particular homologous series and for the same value of $\exp(\alpha T)$

$$b\phi = \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

From what has been discussed about V_s in the previous papers, V_s is the molar volume of the liquid when there is no free volume of the liquid in it and as such it is a function of molecular weight, at least so far as the homologous series are concerned.

$$\text{Whence } b = \exp(\alpha T_s)/C.V_s = {}_1/F(M) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where $F(M)$ represents a function of the molecular weight, M .

Whence $\phi = f(M)$ where $f(M)$ stands for another function of molecular weight.

The function $f(M)$ can be expanded in a power series in M as

$$\phi = a_0 + a_1M + a_2M^2 + \dots$$

where a_0 , a_1 , a_2 , etc. stand for constant coefficients.

Fig. 1
1-Alkenes.

Fig. 2
n-Alkyl cyclohexanes.

Fig. 3
n-Alkanes.

Fig. 4
n-Alkyl benzenes.

Thus, it is established that for a homologous series at the same value of αT , the fluidity ϕ is the same function of molecular weight. Regarding the exact nature of the function nothing can be said *a priori* from a theoretical point of view. For this reason an appeal to experiments reveals the results plotted in Figures 1 to 7. The plots appear to be linear with a negative slope indicating that fluidity at same αT diminishes with molecular weight in a linear manner *i.e.*,

$$\phi = a_0 + a_1 M \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where a_0 and a_1 are positive and negative quantities respectively.

From the above it can be concluded that at constant $\exp(\alpha T)$ the fluidities of the members of the same homologous series diminish as the molecular weight increases *i.e.*, as we ascend higher up in the series. This conclusion is arrived at from experimental data helped by theoretical considerations as set forth in equation (1). McLeod (*loc. cit.*) concluded that since viscosity was connected with free space, the viscosities should be suitably compared at equal free space, *i.e.*, at temperatures where free space may be shown to be the same. In the present case free space is equivalent to $\exp \alpha(T - T_s)$ and since in a homologous series $\exp(\alpha T_s)$ is constant for a given series, the free space of the homologous series is determined by $\exp(\alpha T)$. Since in this case fluidities have been compared at constant $\exp(\alpha T)$, it is tantamount to a comparison at the same free volume as advocated by McLeod (*loc. cit.*). The advantage of the mode of approach presented herein consists in the fact that the relationship between fluidity and molecular weight becomes directly evident through the term 'b' but the exact nature of the function has been known only by appeal to experiments. The relationship derived has been a linear one between ϕ and M with a negative slope. In this respect it differs from the relation suggested by McLeod where he connects viscosity coefficient with molecular weight,

Fig. 5
n-Alkyl cyclopentanes.

Fig. 6
Thiols-1.

Fig. 7
Thiols-2.

Another advantage has been that the present method of approach is free from any arbitrary assumptions but follows directly from the concept of free volume.

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